

**USE OF PUMPING STATIONS AND THE INFLUENCE OF
DEFORMATIONS ON THEIR WATER DELIVERY CHANNELS.****Fayzullayev Joxon Toshpo'lat o'g'li**Institute of counter-irrigation and agrotechnologies
of the National Research University "TIQXMMI".<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14439805>

Annotation: On the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, internal water resources are formed in the system of water management, there are several problems that cause discomfort in the state of Use, and to eliminate these, many scientific works are being carried out on these, articles are being prepared in order to solve this problem, and with them changes are being made and problems are being solved

Keywords: Channels, filtration, leaks, maintenance

As we know, the movement of jets occurs only in the turbulent mode movement of the current. As a result of the presence of vertical organizing speeds, the current carries (transports) sediment (flows) with it on the bottom and side slopes in the direction of the current. If there are no leaks in the incoming flow structure, the above situation will be appropriate. If the incoming flow is high in the amount of leaks, then the opposite happens, that is, the deposition of leaks. In both of these cases, the formation of the esophagus occurs. In the first case, there is a deepening and expansion of the oesophagus, and in the second case, the rise of the slopes of the canal bottom and the sides. In both of these cases, the ravine continues until its own dimensions correspond to the speed and flow modes of the current. In other words, the flow rate transports leaks to a state under the bottom that does not move the material, and also to a uniform flow depth

$$\rho_{mp} = \frac{\eta v^e}{g R^\alpha \omega_0^k} \quad (1)$$

This formula is called a.S.Obrazovsky got the following formula:

$$\rho_{mp} = \left(\frac{\omega_0}{v_*} \right)^{4/3} \frac{D}{g \beta} \frac{v^3}{R \omega_0} \quad (2)$$

Likewise, S.X.Abalyans [] also

$$\rho_{mp} = k \gamma \frac{\sigma^3}{2g \beta} \frac{v^3}{R \omega_0} \quad (3)$$

It appears that the formulas (1.2) and (1.3) differ from each other only in multiples.

The numerical value of these products is S.X.Abalyans [1] will be equal to 0.018 according to research data. Therefore, the equations (1.2) and (1.3) have the following appearance:

$$\rho_{mp} = 0,018v^3 / (H_{cp}\omega_0) \quad (4)$$

K.I.Rossinsky and M.A.Taking Velikanov's[11] $\nu/(H_{or}\omega_0)^{0,33}$ ratio as a basis, he derived the formula in his house for the ($d > 0,05mm$) transport of self-formation fractions:

$$\rho_{mp} = 0,024v^3 / (H_{cp}\omega_0) \quad (5)$$

(1.1) after comparing the formula with (1.2) and (1.5) formulas

$$\rho_{mp} = \eta v^3 / H\omega_0 \quad (6)$$

B.K.Balakayev in his scientific work summarized his research on the exploitation of the Karakum canal and scientific research work on the transport possibilities of the stream. The transport capacity of the stream by it was calculated according to the following experimental data:

$$Q = 100M^3 / c, \quad \nu = 0,95M / c, \quad H_{cp} = 2,3m, \quad b = 40M, \quad I = 0,00012, \quad \omega = 105M^2, \quad R = 2M, \\ C = 50,7\nu / c^{0,5}, \quad n = 0,0225, \quad \omega_0 = 0,48MM / c, \quad \gamma_{cm} = 2,65m / M^3, \quad \gamma = 1m / M^3, \quad \rho_{mp} = 2,585\kappa z / M^3.$$

Its values are Y.A.Ibad-zade formula (+7%), I.F.Carasev formula (-7.2%) and B.K.Balakayev's formulas give satisfactory results when compared with calculated values (2.3%). It should be mentioned that B.K.To form Balakayev's formula, I.F.Karasev used the following formula:

$$\rho_{mp} = \frac{0,000\gamma C^2 M^3 \sqrt{g}}{g^2 H (\gamma_1 - \gamma) (0,755\nu \sqrt{g} + 0,5\omega_0 C)} B\eta\varepsilon,$$

$$B = \frac{\rho}{\rho_{II}} = \frac{\omega_0 C + 0,7\nu \sqrt{g}}{12\omega_0 C} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{12\omega_0 C}{\omega_0 C + 0,7\nu \sqrt{g}}} \right);$$

$$\eta = 1,08 - 0,58 \left(\frac{\nu_c}{\nu} \right)^2; \quad \varepsilon = 1,0 - 0,18 \frac{\omega_0 C}{\nu \sqrt{g}}$$

where is the break rate determined by the Formula S. YE.Mirshuluva. B.K.Balakayev goes to two limitations: does not take into account, i.e., the expression for fine sandy grunts under the conditions of the Karakum Canal; takes the B values of the fine fractional flows of the Karakum canal as relatively robust and equal to 0.84.

1.1-jadval

Muallif	Formula	
V.V.Poslavskiy	$0,009 \frac{v^3}{R^{1/3} \omega_0}$	$\frac{4,143}{+60}$
G.S.Chekulayev	$0,141 \frac{v^{3/2}}{R^{1/6} \sqrt{\omega_0}}$	$\frac{3,075}{+19}$
G.O.Xorst	$0,025 \frac{v^3}{R^{1/3} \omega_0}$	$\frac{11,52}{+340}$
A.N.Gostunskiy	$0,051 \frac{v^3}{R^{3/2} \omega_0}$	$\frac{10,5}{+306}$
S.X.Abalyans	$0,018 \frac{v^3}{R \omega_0}$	$\frac{5,491}{+112,5}$
A.G.Xachatryan	$0,69 \frac{v^{3/2}}{(R \omega_0)^{1/2}}$	$\frac{4,354}{+68,3}$
YE.A.Zamarin	$11v \sqrt{\frac{Rv_i}{\omega_0}}$	$\frac{4,354}{+68,3}$
A.V.Karaushev	$\frac{P^0 \Gamma}{Q}$ $P_s^0 = S_{\text{gsm}} = \Gamma \cdot 0,00057 N \frac{v_H^2}{H} \Gamma$	$\frac{4,802}{+85,5}$
I.F.Karasev	$\frac{0,00015 \gamma C^2 v^3 \sqrt{g}}{g^2 H (\gamma_{cm} - \gamma) (0,755 v \sqrt{g} + 0,5 \omega_0 C)}$	$B \eta \varepsilon \frac{2,39}{-7,2}$
B.K.Balakayev	$0,0053 \frac{\gamma C^2 v^2}{H (\gamma_{cm} - \gamma)} \eta \varepsilon$	$\frac{2,645}{+2,3}$
Y.A.Ibad-zade	$0,029 \left[\sqrt{13 + \omega_0} - 3,6 \right] \rho_{\text{hav}} \frac{v^3}{g H \omega_0}$	$\frac{2,76}{+7}$

S.G.The above experimental data was used by Azizov, I.F.Karasev and B.K.The balakayev's formula_structured values were calculated.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Mamajonov M. Nasoslar va nasos stansiyalari. Darslik, T.:“Fan va texnologiya”, 2012. - 372 bet.
2. Muxammadiyev M.M., Uralov B.R., Mamajonov M., Majidov T.SH., Nizamov O.H., Badalov A.S., Kan E.K.Gidromashinalar. O’quv qo’llanma, Toshkent, TIMI,2010.-193 bet. 115
3. Latipov K.SH. Gidravlika, gidromashinalar va gidroyuritmalar Darslik, Toshkent, O’qituvchi, 1992.- 335 b.

4. Arifjanov A.M.,Q.T.Raximov.,A.K.Xodjiyev *Gidravlika.-Toshkent, TIMI, 2016 y.*
5. Joxon Toshpo'lat o'g F. et al. AMU-QASHQADARYO ITHBDA ISHLATILAYOTGAN NASOS STANSIYALARINING IQLIM KO 'RSATKICHLARINI TADQIQOTI //Journal of new century innovations. – 2022. – T. 14. – №. 1. – C. 161-164.
6. Ibroximovich A. A. et al. MARKAZDAN QOCHMA KOMPRESSOR //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – T. 41. – №. 2. – C. 216-219.
7. Ibroximovich, Abdirazakov Akbar, Fayzullayev Joxon Toshpo'lat o'g, and Xo'jaqulov Nodirbek. "MARKAZDAN QOCHMA KOMPRESSOR." Journal of new century innovations 41.2 (2023): 216-219.
8. Fayzullayev J. et al. GIDROTEXNIKA INSHOOTLARIDA NASOS AGREGATINI FOYDALANISHGA TAYYORLASH, ISHGA TUSHIRISH, VA TOPSHIRISH SINOVLARI //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 12 Part 2. – C. 262-266.
9. Joxon Toshpo'lat o'g F. et al. AMU-QASHQADARYO ITHBDA ISHLATILAYOTGAN NASOS STANSIYALARINING IQLIM KO 'RSATKICHLARINI TADQIQOTI //Journal of new century innovations. – 2022. – T. 14. – №. 1. – C. 161-164.
10. Joxon Toshpo'lat o'g F. et al. KANALNI HISOBLASH ALGORITMI TURLI DONADORLIKDAGI TUPROQLARDA DEFORMATSIYA HOLATI //TADQIQOTLAR. UZ. – 2024. – T. 48. – №. 1. – C. 40-43.

